

ECONOMY

THE FIGHT AGAINST WATER SHORTAGE - A GLOBAL CHALLENGE

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Abstract

The presented article examines the issue of water scarcity that is affecting our humanity. In the study, the distribution of world water resources, the impact of human activities on water availability, the main sources of pollution of natural waters, the existing water supply were extensively analyzed, forecasts and recommendations were reflected due to the increasing demand for water use in agriculture and industry. It was emphasized that implementing uncompromising measures at the state level is crucial to prevent widespread pollution. The article also demonstrates the situation regarding water resources and their use in the republic of Azerbaijan.

The relevance of researching the problem of water scarcity, providing different approaches and solutions to overcome this problem lies in the fact that about 25 percent of the world's population lives in 36 countries with extremely high water stress, where they suffer from this issue and may potentially lead to a complete depletion of water resources in the future.

To conduct a more detailed investigation of the topic studied in the article, the study analyzed materials, articles, and books related to water scarcity in the world and in Azerbaijan, and utilized the historical-comparative method to investigate the causes of water scarcity and to compare the percentage indicators of water scarcity from several years ago to present day.

Keywords: depletion of water resources, environment, pollution, water conflicts, consumption, water supply, water shortage, infrastructure.

Introduction.

Water is a limited and precious natural resource that is essential for life and cannot be replaced by any other substances. Access to safe water should be recognized as a fundamental human right. In other words, water should be seen as a social value. The solution to the water problem must first be started by questioning people's views on water. Unfortunately, common expressions such as " " " " create the impression that water is inexhaustible, cheap, and insignificant resource. It is more difficult to accustom a person brought up with these thoughts to save water.

Water scarcity is defined as the lack of access to safe water, and the unconscious consumption of water. Access to fresh water decreases as the world's population grows, and the climate changes become more frequent. Currently, 785 million people around world lack access to clean drinking water, and over 800 children die every day from diarrhea caused by unsafe water, sanitation, and hygiene. Without adequate access to clean water, people can remain trapped in poverty for generations.

According to the World Resources Institute, 36 countries are already experiencing high water stress, including Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Armenia, and Kyrgyzstan. Azerbaijan is among the countries with moderate water stress, while Tajikistan, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, and Kazakhstan are also on the list [8]. This means that the demand for water resources for settlements, industries, and agriculture is already exceeding

the available supply. The rapid growth of the world's population and climate change exacerbate this problem, causing some regions to receive too much water, while others become more arid and desertified [8].

It is well-known that since the middle of the 20th century, the countries in the Middle East, North Africa, Central Asia, and Southeast Asia have experienced the pressing issues of poverty, food shortages, rising prices, unemployment, corruption, and organized crime, many of which are linked to water scarcity. The availability of fresh water is a critical factor in the region, and its scarcity can have significant impact on domestic politics [2].

Water is used in different ways across the world. In fact, 3,500-3,600 km³ of water is used annually in agriculture in the world, 70% of which is used for irrigation. The amount of water used in agriculture is 3-4 times higher than the amount used in industry. Another area of water use is for domestic and household purposes. Only 4% of the world's population has enough water, which is 300-400 liters per person per day, of which 10% is high-quality drinking water.

According to the international conference in Rio de Janeiro, one in three people in developing countries suffers from a lack of drinking water. 80% of diseases and 1/3 of deaths worldwide are related to inadequate access to clean water and poor sanitation. Therefore, providing high-quality water to the world's population is one of the main issues [2].

In 1977, the global community first expressed concern about the depletion, pollution, and irrational use of water resources by evaluating the global risk probabilities and the predictions. In the same year, the First United Nations Conference on World Water Resources was held in Mar de Plata, Argentina, where delegates agreed to assess the global nature of hydrological problems, promote interstate cooperation in this direction, and launch the "International Fresh Water and Sanitation" decade. In this regard, the Dublin Conference in 1992 was also successful in developing first principles of international cooperation in the direction of solving fresh water problems. In the document, known as the "Dublin Principles", the importance of protecting and managing water resources through joint efforts, recognizing the economic and social value of water, and acknowledging the limited nature of freshwater resources were emphasized [14].

The issue of global freshwater problems was extensively discussed at the UN Millennium Summit. The document titled "Millennium Development Goals," adopted during the summit, set a primary objective for the 193 member states of the international community and 23 international organizations: to reduce by 2015 the number of people lacking access to freshwater resources and basic sanitation. Throughout human history, approximately 3,600 agreements have been concluded on the control and use of water sources. Among these agreements, the first document specifically addressing international rivers was the "Rules for the Use of International Rivers," which originated from the session of the International Law Association held in Helsinki in 1966 and became known as the "Helsinki Rules." The "Helsinki Rules" encompassed a wide range of procedural rules, including the control of transboundary waters, prevention of pollution, regulation of vessel traffic, and the resolution of interstate disputes through peaceful means. Notably, the Helsinki Rules introduced the principle of conscious and equitable utilization of water resources as the foundation for establishing a legal framework governing the exploitation of transboundary waters. According to this principle, each state should utilize transboundary waters within its territory based on its essential needs while considering the rights of other neighboring states [14].

While the situation regarding the water resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan and their management is indeed challenging, it is not without hope. The country faces certain difficulties in controlling and utilizing its freshwater sources. Situated in an arid zone, Azerbaijan significantly lags behind other countries in the South Caucasus region and neighboring Russian Federation when it comes to surface water resources per square kilometer of its territory and per capita. Surprisingly, Georgia holds 62% of the total water resources in the Southern Caucasus, followed by Armenia with 28%, while Azerbaijan only has access to 10%. On average, approximately 10-14 cubic kilometers of water are extracted from natural resources annually, with agriculture accounting for 60-70% of usage, and industry utilizing 20-25% [7].

While the country possesses 4.6 million hectares of agriculturally suitable land, only 1.45 million hectares are currently under irrigation, with 90% of agricultural production taking place in these areas. Unfortunately, until 2012, comprehensive reclamation efforts were able to cover only 610 thousand hectares of those irrigated lands [7].

The ecological situation in the Araz River is alarmingly worse compared to the Kura River. Beginning from Gyumri and extending to the border region with Nakhchivan AR, the Araz River receives untreated domestic and industrial wastewater from over 10 industrial cities in Armenia. Moreover, the Gederchay, Vorotan, and Akhuryan rivers, which flow into the Araz River from the enemy's territory, have been severely contaminated. These rivers exhibit extremely low oxygen levels, with an acidity indicator dropping to pH 2.4. The microflora in the water decreases by 180-200 times, and the vegetation along the river banks is also devastated. Additionally, one of the most polluted rivers of Araz is Okchuchay [3].

The chemical composition of the Kura and Araz rivers, as well as their tributaries, has undergone significant changes due to the growing impact of human activities. Over the past 40 years, the mineral content of the Kura River near the city of Salyan, Azerbaijan, has more than tripled, reaching 1020 mg/l. Similarly, water mineralization in the Saatli area of the Araz River has increased from 400 mg/l to 1300 mg/l. Previously classified as hydrocarbon and calcium-rich, the rivers' water now falls into the sulfate-sodium category. The primary factor responsible for these shifts in chemical composition and water quality is the discharge of water from irrigated fields and collector drainage into the Kura River and its tributaries. Furthermore, recently, pollution has been observed in rivers that are not directly connected to the Kura-Araz basins but flow directly into the Caspian Sea. These include rivers in the northeastern part of the Greater Caucasus and the Lankaran natural region, such as Gusarchay, Gudyalchay, Valvalechay, Karachay, Atachay, Gilgilchay in the Guba-Khachmaz region, and Lankaranchay, Vilashchay, and others in the Lankaran region. These rivers face continuous pollution from settlements and agro-industrial farms [3].

How does the water crisis affect the economy?

The search for a safe water source consumes a significant amount of time, resulting in billions of dollars in lost economic opportunities. A staggering 785 million people worldwide still lack access to safe water, with women often bearing the burden of water collection. They spend hours each day, repeatedly queuing at crowded water kiosks or embarking on long journeys to distant sources like rivers and ponds. This time is wasted, no income is earned. The economic impact of inadequate access to basic water and sanitation is profound, with an estimated global loss of \$260 billion annually [12].

Water scarcity has significant economic implications, particularly in the agricultural sector. While agriculture itself contributes to water scarcity, it also heavily relies on this precious resource. The consequences of water scarcity on agriculture are evident in various

regions, such as Morocco, where the depletion of water resources has resulted in environmental degradation and a staggering estimated loss of around US\$350 million in agricultural land use. The impact of water scarcity extends beyond Morocco. Countries like India, China, and those in the Middle East are grappling with severe drought conditions, severely affecting farm production and causing a dangerous surge in food prices [13].

Priority should be given to the efficient utilization of local water resources to meet the growing water demand, while also ensuring that the transfer of water from neighboring basins does not exceed a certain threshold of the total demand. Preserving the delicate balance of the existing ecosystem within the water basin is paramount. It is crucial to avoid falling into a vicious cycle where attempts to address one problem inadvertently create multiple other challenges. Moreover, excessive reliance on external water sources carries inherent risks. The availability of water from other basins is not guaranteed, and the water basin itself may face the imminent threat of drought.

Many agricultural fields still rely on simple flood or surface irrigation as their primary method of watering crops. However, this traditional approach often leads to excessive water application, resulting in waterlogging of fields and significant water losses due to evaporation and transport. Promoting farmer education about potential water loss, establishing water-use reduction targets, enhancing irrigation methods, and providing financial support for water-saving technologies are essential steps towards mitigating wasteful water usage in agriculture.

Rising food prices and water shortages are intensifying regional conflicts and prompting people to migrate towards regions with readily available water

sources. Water scarcity leads to a scarcity of food, causing an increase in commodity prices and impeding trade with developing economies. This situation ultimately leads to social unrest and conflicts over water resources. Water scarcity not only affects rainfed and irrigated agriculture but also has a direct impact on animal husbandry and an indirect impact on the food processing industry [13].

The problem was investigated using a survey method, with the participation of approximately 3,000 individuals. The survey revealed that 6.4% of respondents were unaware of water scarcity, while 93.6% were aware of it. Furthermore, 43.2% of the population reported experiencing water shortages in their region, while 56.8% did not face any issues. The survey also aimed to identify the water conservation goals of the citizens. Additionally, participants were asked to rate the quality of their local freshwater supply on a scale of 1 to 10. Based on the feedback received, many individuals expressed concerns about the cleanliness of the water and its unsuitability for drinking due to the presence of chlorine. Finally, respondents were asked to propose steps to address this problem. Various approaches were suggested, including educational campaigns, the adoption of new technologies, desalination methods, water meter limitations, equitable distribution of water resources and so on.

In summary, it is evident that people are facing a severe water shortage and expressing their dissatisfaction with the current situation. Failure to address this problem could have grave consequences, including potential conflicts, both domestically and globally.

The percentage breakdown of population awareness regarding the issue of water shortage in the world is as follows:

It appears that a majority of people are confronted with this problem and endure its consequences.

The breakdown of water scarcity percentages in the regions is as follows:

When questioned about people's objectives in conserving water in their daily usage, it emerged that 65.2% expressed concerns over the diminishing water

resources, 20.1% were apprehensive about high meter readings, and 8.6% admitted to not making any efforts to save water. Additionally, approximately 6% of individuals stated that they save water due to their belief that wasting it is sinful.

Conclusion and suggestions.

Due to pollution, excessive evaporation, and unsustainable consumption, the world's freshwater resources are depleting at an alarming rate. Addressing water scarcity requires a comprehensive approach that integrates various disciplines. Effective management of water resources is essential to ensure equitable socio-economic development while preserving the integrity of the ecosystems.

The following recommendations have been proposed to enhance water infrastructure and alleviate pressure on freshwater supplies:

1. The highest quality standards must be met for the water used for drinking and daily purposes.
2. New wells should be dug, damaged ones should be repaired, and leaking wells should be closed.
3. The prevention of artificial damming and alteration of river courses should be prioritized.
4. Special reservoirs and water pools should be built.
5. Working groups should be established for comprehensive assessment and analysis of water resources.
6. Information sessions and seminars on water management should be organized to educate people about responsible water consumption.
7. The improvement of irrigation techniques and the application of modern measurement technologies should be pursued.
8. The cleanliness of surface water sources should be ensured, and the number of water treatment facilities should be increased with funds allocated by the government.
9. The constitutional guarantee of the right to access water should be upheld.
10. Natural ecosystems, such as wetlands and forests, which play a vital role in collecting, filtering, storing, and releasing water, should be protected and restored. Drained wetlands should be re-watered.
11. The reuse of wastewater should be promoted in urban areas with growing populations and limited water supplies, while efforts should be made to reduce the discharge of polluted water to improve the quality of rivers and lakes.

It is crucial for governments to invest in infrastructure, while individuals and businesses must collaborate in a sustained and coordinated effort to alleviate long-

term water scarcity. In summary, it should be emphasized that failure to take necessary measures poses a significant threat to national security, as severe droughts loom not only for our country but also for other nations in the future.

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